

The International Education Seminar, October Teacher Festivals, Diversity and Inclusion Seminars, and Teachers Without Borders Program: strategies for teacher training in the municipality of Fortaleza

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses strategies for expanding teacher training through events aimed at increasing access to information for municipal employees in Fortaleza. In this sense, we analyze the relevance of the 1st International Education Seminar - "Educational Perspectives for the 21st Century: Towards quality education with equity; 1st Municipal Seminar on Diversity and Inclusion: A welcoming school; 2nd Municipal Seminar on Diversity and Inclusion: Dialogues for education with equity; 1st and 2nd edition of the October Teacher International Festival. A methodology characterized as qualitative was employed. Additionally, bibliographic research was complemented with input from the Municipality's Secretary of Education and personal insights shared by the authors regarding the educational events mentioned throughout the article. The main objective of this study is to analyze literature and discourse on teacher training strategies in the municipality of Fortaleza. As a final result, it became evident that the teacher training strategies implemented in Fortaleza have made significant efforts to qualify educators, thus enhancing teaching in municipal schools. However, it is crucial to emphasize that these initiatives should continue and improve to reach an increasing number of educators and promote a more inclusive, diversified, and high-quality education for all students.

Keywords: *Education, Teacher Training, Improvement of Teaching and Learning.*

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I. INTRODUCTION

In the realm of contemporary education, teacher training stands as a topic of paramount importance due to its direct impact on the quality of education provided in schools, as well as on the academic and personal

development of students. This holds true in the municipality of Fortaleza, CE, where the municipal Department of Education has prioritized the implementation of effective teacher training strategies.

A methodology characterized as qualitative was employed in this study. Additionally, bibliographic research was complemented with input from the Municipality's Secretary of Education and personal insights shared by the authors regarding the educational events mentioned throughout the article.

The primary objective of this study is to analyze the literature and discourse concerning teacher training strategies in the municipality of Fortaleza. To achieve this goal, the following specific objectives were established: 1) to conduct bibliographic research on the educational events promoted by the municipality of Fortaleza regarding teacher training; 2) to obtain the opinions of the Secretary of Education of the municipality of Fortaleza regarding these events.

This study is organized into four sections. The first section comprises the introduction, where the research objectives are highlighted. The second section outlines the methodological procedures adopted for the study's development. The third section provides a theoretical foundation, while the fourth section presents the final considerations.

The aim of this study is to provide a better understanding of teacher training strategies in Fortaleza and to offer valuable insights into educational practices both locally and internationally. This is achieved through a combination of bibliographic research, input from the Secretary of Education, and the perspectives of the authors.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A qualitative method was employed in this study to gain a profound understanding of the teacher training strategies implemented in the municipality of Fortaleza, CE. The qualitative approach was chosen to facilitate a thorough and contextualized analysis of the educational practices in question, as well as the perceptions and experiences of those involved [1].

The study was conducted in two main phases: firstly, a literature review was conducted followed by obtaining the opinions of the Secretary of Education of the municipality of Fortaleza. Secondly, throughout the article, the authors sought to develop their impressions, collected from observations made during each event mentioned in the article [1].

The purpose of conducting a literature review was to provide a comprehensive review of the literature on the topic of teacher training in the municipality of Fortaleza. The literature review provided a solid theoretical foundation for analyzing and discussing the results [1].

The collection of opinions presented by the Secretary of Education was through interviews aimed at obtaining information about the current teacher training strategies, their goals, their effects, and the challenges faced in the implementation process. A better understanding of the municipality's educational policies and practices was achieved through these interviews [1].

The authors' impressions examined and interpreted the data collected by researching literature and interviewing the Secretary of Education. From this information, reflections and impressions were made about the teacher training strategies in Fortaleza, highlighting their strengths, challenges, and potential areas for improvement [1].

III. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 Strategies for Continued Education in the Municipality of Fortaleza

In an endeavor to increasingly promote opportunities for quality education for its students, the Municipal Department of Education (SME) of Fortaleza has been developing various initiatives aimed at the qualification of its teachers, as well as other municipal employees. In this regard, we present below some events held during the academic year to reaffirm the need for continued education as an essential element for the improvement of teaching actions.

3.1.1 1st International Education Seminar - "Educational Perspectives for the 21st Century: Towards quality education with equity".

This event, organized by the SME, took place from September 26th to 28th, 2019, at the Ceará Events Center and brought together approximately 2500 professionals from the Municipal Education Network, including teachers, principals, coordinators, technicians, and guests. It is noteworthy that this event featured the participation of prominent national and international figures who are references in the field of education. Therefore, its main objective was to foster discussion about public education in the current scenario, considering the political, social, and economic context from the perspective of quality education with equity. In this aspect, the International Seminar played an important role in defining the actions of the SME regarding the implementation of the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC), as it promoted discussions and reflections

on pedagogical concepts that assisted in the redefinition of the Political-Pedagogical Projects (PPP) of municipal schools [2].

On the first day, the aforementioned Seminar featured relevant lectures such as the keynote address by Professor Leandro Karnal, who addressed the theme "21st Century: Challenges of Brazilian Education". On the second day of the event, from 8:00 am to 10:00 am, scientific papers were presented by professionals from the Municipal Network, with the article "Raising Awareness: Promoting the awareness of the need for an inclusive school in a municipal school of Fortaleza" among the 32 selected papers, authored by one of the authors of this study. There were also eight morning lectures on various topics including Integral Education, Inclusive Education, Teacher Training, Educational Innovation, Curriculum, Early Childhood Education, Results-Oriented Management, and Educational Evaluation, addressed by national and international speakers, as well as SME technicians, who presented innovative and successful municipal management experiences. Among the speakers were Professor Sara Barros from Portugal, Professor Júlio César Furtado from Rio de Janeiro, Marina de Cuffa from the Ayrton Senna Institute, among others. Participants could also choose to attend the experience in Relational Psychomotricity [2].

In the afternoon sessions, thematic panels took place. The first panel addressed "Education financing in the context of quality with equity", featuring presentations by Aléssio Lima, president of Undime - Northeast Region; Federal Deputy Idilvan Alencar; José Cavalcante Arnaud, professor at the State University of Ceará (UECE) and the Doctorate Program in Public Policies (CAPES). The second panel focused on "Early Childhood: fulfilling rights, laying the foundation for educational quality", with the participation of Professor Sara Barros Araújo from Portugal, Fortaleza Health Secretary Joana Maciel, and Professor Daniel Santos from the University of São Paulo (USP). The panels were moderated by Fábio Pannunzio, journalist from TV Bandeirantes [2].

On the third day, starting at 8:00 am, the program began with artistic presentations followed by the panel "Indicator of Inequality and Learning (IDEA): the school and the right to learn", with the participation of Professor Chico Soares from Insper; Professor José Romão from UNINOCE/Instituto Paulo Freire; Professor Almerindo Janela from Portugal; and Professor Dalila Saldanha, Education Secretary of Fortaleza. The panel was moderated by Cristiano Reckziegel, journalist from Canal Futura [2]. On this day, the audience also had the opportunity to attend the keynote address "Education in contemporaneity: the necessary school", delivered by Professor Viviane Mosé. The Seminar was concluded by the poet and cordelist Bráulio Bessa [2].

It is evident that this event was of great value for the expansion of knowledge of the municipal employees involved, and it allowed the discussions promoted therein to be shared, as they were published in a digital book [8].

3.1.2 Municipality of Fortaleza: 1st Municipal Seminar on Diversity and Inclusion: School that Welcomes

The Municipality of Fortaleza, through the Municipal Department of Education (SME), organized the "1st Municipal Seminar on Diversity and Inclusion: School that Welcomes" on August 24th and 25th, 2022, held at the Ceará Events Center. The event aimed to engage approximately 6,000 professionals from the capital's education network [3].

During the opening of the event, the municipality's Secretary of Education, Dalila Saldanha, emphasized the significance of the seminar, stating: "Today marks the beginning of a journey where inclusion and diversity will be part of the entire educational agenda of Fortaleza, from in-context training to ongoing events." She also highlighted the challenges and the need for continuous improvement in the perspective of inclusion and ensuring better learning conditions for students with disabilities through Specialized Educational Assistance (SEA) tailored to this target audience [3].

To provide the school community with spaces for discussion on the topic over the two days, the agenda included lectures, thematic panels, cultural attractions, and stories of resilience and overcoming challenges from students, families, and teachers from school units. Professor Francisco Soares from UFMG delivered the lecture "Equity from the Perspective of Diversity and Inclusion" [4].

During the activities at the Events Center, participants had the opportunity to explore the exhibition "On the Fingertips," part of the collection of the Fortaleza Photography Museum (MFF). The exhibit comprises 20 works produced during photography training for the blind and visually impaired, enabling tactile perception of the images. Among the tools used is audio description, making graphic representation a democratic and accessible art form [4].

On the morning of the 25th, educators attended the following lectures: "Inclusive Education in the Fortaleza Network" by Dalila Saldanha (Municipal Secretary of Education of Fortaleza); Keynote Address: "Word is Power!" by Elisa Lucinda (Actress and Poet); Thematic Panel: "Pathways to Building an Inclusive School" with Prof. Sumika Soares (UFES); Prof. Rita Magalhães (UFRN), and Prof. Juliana Santana (UECE); Moderated by Prof. Jammes Mendes (SME). Additionally, there was a musical performance by Amora, a student from EM Rogaciano Leite [3].

The afternoon session began with a performance by the “Pisada Especial Forró Group”, followed by the lecture "Equity from the Perspective of Diversity and Inclusion" by Prof. Francisco Soares (UFMG). Panels included "Reports of Resilience, Coping, and Overcoming Challenges" featuring Amora, a student from EM Rogaciano Leite; Antonio David Sousa de Almeida, a former student from EM Adroaldo Teixeira Castelo; Virginia Castro, mother of Artur Oliveira, a student from EM Tomaz Pompeu; and Prof. Patricia Adjoke (SDHDS). There were also thematic panels on "School Inclusion: Everyone's Responsibility" moderated by Prof. Ângelo Oliveira (IFCE-Quixadá) and Prof. Mônica Costa (SME) [3].

3.1.3 2nd Municipal Seminar on Diversity and Inclusion: Dialogues for Equity in Education

Continuing its efforts to enhance the capabilities of its staff, the Municipality of Fortaleza, through the Municipal Department of Education (SME), organized the "2nd Municipal Seminar on Diversity and Inclusion: Dialogues for Equity in Education" on September 4th and 5th, 2023, at the Ceará Events Center - Icapuí Hall, Gate D. It is noteworthy that the event brought together approximately 4,000 professionals from the Municipal Education Network [5].

The second edition of the seminar featured the participation of prominent figures in the field of Diverse and Inclusive Education, including lectures, thematic panels, testimonials, sensory experiences, cultural presentations, and an art exhibition space. The event aimed to provide moments of reflection for the school community on the challenges and possibilities of inclusive education in contemporary times. Thus, the Municipal Network seeks to broaden discussions and strengthen pedagogical practices, promoting educational processes that meet the needs of professionals and students [4]; [6].

It is observed that the agenda targets all those involved in the municipal school system, including teachers, inclusion assistants, pedagogical coordinators, support professionals, principals, and educational counselors, stationed at schools, Early Childhood Education Centers, and partner daycare centers. Regarding inclusion in the Municipal Network, the Education System offers students with disabilities, Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), and High Abilities/Giftedness full access to education within regular schools. In this context, the Municipality organizes various actions that encompass the implementation and provision of services for Inclusive Education. Currently, according to data from the 2022 School Census, Fortaleza ranks as the 3rd capital in Brazil and the 1st in the North and Northeast in enrollments in Inclusive Education [5].

As for Specialized Educational Assistance, enrolled students have access to it in the opposite school shift, either in the 305 Multifunctional Resource Rooms (SRM), in affiliated institutions, or through inclusive pedagogical practices in regular classrooms. The Municipal Network also has 644 school support professionals and 766 inclusion assistants who provide support to these students. Additionally, it has agreements with seven institutions for the provision of Specialized Educational Assistance [5].

At the school where the authors of this study teach, the movement for inclusion has been a constant endeavor, as mentioned previously. Actions promoting inclusivity occur throughout the academic year, with particular emphasis during April and September during the inclusion weeks. These initiatives are now planned collaboratively with regular classroom teachers and Specialized Educational Assistance teachers to provide conditions that facilitate learning for all. In this edition of the Seminar, our school had the participation of our students from the "Moon Band Project," composed of students with and without disabilities. Additionally, there was the "Autistic Protagonism Project," in which autistic students lecture on autism, and the participation of a mother who is part of the School of Parents Project developed at the school for parents of students with disabilities. Ultimately, these initiatives from the SME encourage its teachers to go above and beyond and seek knowledge to fulfill their role in the inclusion of all their students [5].

3.1.4 International Teacher October Festival: 1st Edition

In acknowledgment of the role of teachers, their dedication, and commitment to their students, the Municipality of Fortaleza, through the Municipal Department of Education (SME), has been offering its employees a week of exchanging experiences and sharing knowledge, in addition to cultural activities.

The Municipality of Fortaleza held the 1st edition of the October Teacher Festival from October 21st to 27th, 2022, at the Ceará Events Center, with a program aimed at connecting knowledge, protagonism, diversity, inclusion, hospitality, and innovation. The event welcomed approximately 12,000 professionals throughout the week and consisted of content tracks addressing current topics relevant to the training of municipal educators. The event's diversity lies in the variety and simultaneity of activities offered throughout the week, including lectures, discussions, workshops, art exhibitions, and cultural shows. The program takes place in celebration of Teacher's Month in the Municipal Network [7].

It is noteworthy that the schedule of the October Teacher Festival was integrated into the 2022 continuing education calendar for teachers in the school units, and it brought diversified actions, including workshops focused on the emotional and physical health of teachers and lectures by recognized professionals in the educational field.

The activities also included spaces for meditation and yoga, relational psychomotricity, a stage for showcasing teacher talents, and services such as vaccination booths. Additionally, there were musical performances by local bands during break times and in the late afternoon [6].

On Friday (10/21), the first day of the festival, the program featured presentations of 60 works from the "Author Teacher: Making History... Exchanging Stickers 2023" project. The project has been running since 2017 and aims to encourage the culture of sharing experiences among teachers. On the same day, the II Colloquium on Education in Fortaleza took place, featuring works by teachers from the Network who are enrolled in master's and doctoral programs at partner universities, as part of the Fortaleza Observatory Program. Additionally, throughout the program, the most current pedagogical research developed by graduate programs will be presented.

For the Early Childhood Education audience, highlights included the participation of pediatrician and public health expert Dr. Daniel Becker, with the lecture "The child who plays is happier! Free play, saying no to consumerism, and early exposure to screens"; Prof. Beatriz Ferraz, with a workshop on "Learning and development rights of babies and children: reflections on caregiving and education"; and Prof. Mônica Pinazza, with the theme "Teaching in Early Childhood Education: organizing times, spaces, and relationships."

For Elementary Education, activities ranged from workshops on sung toys and games with Prof. Marcelo Serralva, discussions on Reader Formation with Prof. Cleudene Aragão, to a lecture by São Paulo teacher Débora Garofalo, who was the first Brazilian woman and the first South American to be a finalist in the Global Teacher Prize, considered the Nobel Prize of education, being one of the top 10 teachers in the world.

To close the 2022 October Teacher Festival, there was a keynote lecture by the poet and cordelist from Ceará, Bráulio Bessa. French educator Anne Lapiere, co-creator of relational psychomotricity, also gave a lecture on "Training and socioemotional development: teacher care and child development." The farewell of the edition was with the singer and accordionist from Ceará, Waldonys, who performed at the event's closing. Teachers were able to participate in activities according to their interests, with the event's innovation being the construction of their formative tracks [7].

3.1.5 International Teacher October Festival: 2nd Edition

The second edition of the International Teacher October Festival took place from October 16th to 20th, 2023, at the Ceará Events Center. The event celebrates Teacher's Month in the Municipal Education Network. In this edition, the Festival's theme was "Expanding the Frontiers of Education." Teachers were able to participate in the activities on days designated for planning their classes [9].

Each day of the event combined fixed schedules with others specially planned for those specific dates. Highlights included keynote lectures led by Bráulio Bessa (10/16), Viviane Mosé (10/17), José Pacheco (10/18), Carla Akotirene (10/19), and Daniel Becker (10/20).

The agenda focused on current topics aimed at the training of teachers working in the Municipal Education Network. The richness of the Festival lies in the variety and simultaneous realization of activities throughout the week, including lectures, dialogues, workshops, book launches, experiences, cultural shows, playful activities, among others [9].

Secretary Dalila Saldanha stated that the event celebrates the importance of the teaching profession for the full development of society, evidenced by the protagonism of teachers and the positive results achieved in the Fortaleza Municipal Education Network.

"We want to celebrate the pride, recognition, and dedication of our teachers in the execution of the educational policy developed in our teaching units. In another edition of the October Teacher Festival, the agenda was all designed for the well-being of our teachers, providing a welcoming environment that favors teacher protagonism, professional growth, exchange of experiences, cultural activities, and, most importantly, reunions among them," said the secretary.

She also pointed out, "We are the fourth largest education network in Brazil and leaders in inclusive and full-time education in the North and Northeast. In addition, we have innovative programs aimed at valuing teachers, such as financing postgraduate studies and the 'Teacher Without Borders,' which sent 50 teachers for exchanges in France and Spain" [7].

Each day, the Pecém and Taíba halls of the Ceará Events Center hosted a series of flexible activities, allowing participants to choose the experiences they would participate in and customize their agenda. These moments aimed to make the event playful, interactive, and encourage professionals to exchange experiences. Throughout the day, there were book exhibitions, literary environments, talent shows, book launches by Municipal Education Network teachers, cultural shows, among others.

The "Dialogues" program, held simultaneously in 12 activity rooms, allowed each guest to share knowledge on topics that permeate the routine of teachers in the Network [6].

Numerous guests conducted these sessions, including Prof. Dr. Margaret Egan, Prof. Dr. Socorro Acioli, Prof. Dr. Cleudene Aragão, Prof. Dr. Luciane Goldberg, Prof. Dr. Alexandre Santiago, Coletivo Taboa,

Prof. M. Sc. Tâmara Bezerra, Prof. Dr. Juliana Santana, Prof. Patrícia Adjokê, Prof. Dr. Iris Amâncio, among others.

Throughout the Festival, five keynote lectures were planned for the audience's training. On Monday, poet Bráulio Bessa spoke about "Poetry that Transforms." On Tuesday, poet and psychoanalyst Viviane Mosé discussed "Contemporary Challenges - Mental Health and the Value of Life." The following day, Wednesday, José Pacheco, master in Education Sciences and founder of the Escola da Ponte, addressed "New Social Constructions of Learning."

On Thursday, Carla Akotirene, Ph.D. in Gender Studies and creator of Opará Saberes, gave a lecture on "Antiracist Education: How Intersectionality Can Combat Institutional Racism." Finally, closing the lecture series on Friday, pediatrician Daniel Becker discussed the "Challenges for Educators" regarding "Contemporary Childhood and Adolescence."

It is worth noting that the Festival, focusing on the exchange of experiences and production by teachers, held the 3rd Colloquium on Research in Education and Teaching, the 1st Exhibition of Innovative Pedagogical Practices, as well as workshops on educational innovation and relational psychomotricity. All of this aimed to stimulate teachers' production and expand their roles in classroom practice, scientific, textual, and research production. In this sense, the International Teacher October Festival promoted the launch of three volumes of the project "Teacher Author: Making History... Exchanging Stickers," with 92 works by authors from the 2022 edition of the project [9].

Finally, it is important to mention the lecture given by Prof. Dr. Margaret Egan (Ireland), which addressed the History and Evolution of Inclusion in the Irish Education System.

3.1.6 Teachers Without Borders Program

The Teachers Without Borders Program (TWB) is an initiative by the Municipal Education Secretariat (MES) of Fortaleza, aimed at enhancing professional development. Its objective is to provide internationally renowned educational experiences to teachers within the Fortaleza Municipal Public Education Network, in countries recognized worldwide for their contributions to education. It is noteworthy that the pedagogical exchange facilitated by the program enables participating teachers to learn about the most current methodologies and successful practices in education from leading countries in teaching and learning [10].

Selected educators for the exchange participate in a pre-travel course throughout the week at the Darcy Ribeiro Teacher Academy. The purpose of this formative moment is to provide information on the culture, language, and data about the destination country of the exchange, along with other pertinent guidance. [6]

The 48-hour training consists of in-person workshop sessions conducted by two instructors, with at least one being a Portuguese speaker, and another more practical part involving personal work guided by activities proposed during these workshops. The exchange also includes two moments of immersion internships in local schools and group cultural outings [6].

The training comprises five modules: 1 - understanding the educational system of the country (particularities and functioning); 2 - managing diversity in the classroom (inclusive pedagogy - the more practical part of building tools, organizational methods, and appropriate pedagogical approaches); 3 - assessing student progress and knowledge; 4 - understanding the path of cultural and artistic education; and 5 - handling and critically analyzing different digital tools in the classroom [10].

In its fourth edition, the program has already benefited 75 teachers, who had the opportunity to participate in an Education Extension Course in Grenoble/France from October 2 to October 15, 2023, Cáceres/Spain from October 16 to October 29, 2023, and Limerick/Ireland from December 4 to December 15, 2023. These teachers had the opportunity to learn about successful international pedagogical practices and share the knowledge and experiences they gained in the Municipal Education Network [10].

In this fourth edition, 50 spots are being offered for the exchange, with 25 for Ireland and 25 for Portugal. The Education Extension Course in Irish and Portuguese territories will take place simultaneously from September 9 to September 20, 2024 [6].

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

It is concluded that these actions promoted by the SME are contributing to teachers in the Municipal Education Network of Fortaleza expanding their understanding of the need for continuous training, enabling them to adopt new teaching approaches and methodologies favorable to teaching and learning in the public education system.

The research highlights a significant advancement in the field of education and professional development of teachers achieved in the municipality of Fortaleza, CE, through the Teachers Without Borders Program, International Education Seminar, International October Teachers Festival, and Diversity and Inclusion Seminars. Throughout this study, we have seen the importance of these initiatives in promoting a broader and

more comprehensive teacher training, providing them with essential tools and knowledge to address the challenges of the modern classroom.

The International Education Seminar gives educators the opportunity to stay updated on the latest trends and educational practices and exchange experiences with renowned professionals. The International October Teachers Festival serves as an occasion to contemplate and discuss issues related to education and encourages teachers to be creative and inventive.

Diversity and inclusion seminars help educators understand the value of diversity and inclusion in schools and prepare them to deal with heterogeneity in classrooms. Finally, the Teachers Without Borders Program offers teachers enriching experiences in different educational and cultural contexts, promoting the internationalization of education. As a result, it is evident that the teacher training strategies implemented in Fortaleza have made significant efforts to qualify educators, improving teaching in municipal schools.

However, it is essential to emphasize that these initiatives must continue and improve to reach an increasing number of educators and promote a more inclusive, diverse, and high-quality education for all students.

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